

FAIR research data

F: Findable

It should be possible to others to find your data.

A: Accessible

It should be possible for humans and machines to gain access to your data.

I: Interoperable

It should be possible to combine and exchange data from different sources.

R: Reusable

Data should be sufficiently documented to support their reuse.

www.punch4nfdi.de

Fact sheet

- Wilkinson, M. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- FAIR assessment tools:
 - tools to (automatically) measure and assess the FAIRness of data sets
 - different interpretation of the FAIR principles and therefore different implementation of measures
 - examples:
 - F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool by FAIRSFAR
 - FAIR Checker by IFB
 - FAIR Data Self-Assessment Tool by ARDC
- Barker, M. et al. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. Sci Data 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>
- Text blocks on front side based on slides by Rehermann, C. Short Introduction to the FAIR data principles. <https://zenodo.org/records/11380874>

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